

Blinded Assessment of Study Results From Evaluation of the National Tool for Observation of Infection Prevention Measures in the Healthcare (NOST) – a Cluster Randomized Trial

Discussion meeting November 21, 2025

Attendees: Atle Fretheim, Runar Barstad Solberg, Petter Elstrøm, Unni Gopinathan, Mette Fagernes (online), Hanne-Merete Eriksen-Volle (online), Ingeborg Hess Elgersma (minutes, corresponding author: ingeborghess.elgersma@fhi.no)

The protocol and statistical analysis plan have previously been published (Fagernes, M., Eriksen-Volle, H.-M., Holst, C., Rose, C. J., Solberg, R. B., & Elstrøm, P. (2023). Study protocol: Evaluation of the National tool for observation of infection prevention measures in the healthcare (NOST) – a cluster randomized trial. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7648821>; Rose, C., & Elstrøm, P. (2025). Statistical Analysis Plan: Evaluation of the National tool for observation of infection prevention measures in the healthcare (NOST) - a cluster randomized trial. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17368463>)

PE performed the analyses and was de facto not blinded to treatment allocation. The other meeting attendees were blinded to treatment allocation. PE presented blinded results, labelling the treatment arms “Deadheads” and “Led heads”. PE was not involved in the writing of this document.

The intervention was implementing and adhering to the NOST tool for one year compared to not having implemented and adhered to the NOST tool. The intervention effect was estimated using a linear combination of intervention arm and adherence to treatment.

In total 16 hospitals were enrolled in the study. The intervention was stratified by hospital, so that 106 wards were randomised to treatment and control. For Led heads there were complete data regarding the primary outcome from 15 hospitals and 49/53 wards (92%). For Deadheads there were complete data from 12 hospitals and 36/53 wards (68%). Because the rate of missing data was higher than the set limit of 5%, multiple imputation was used when estimating the results regarding the primary outcome.

The primary outcome was compliance with the hand hygiene recommendations by hospital staff. The number of observations and compliances were aggregated to the hospital ward level.

The risk ratio if deadheads received the intervention was 0.99 (95% confidence interval 0.85 to 1.15). The risk ratio if lead heads received the intervention was 0.77 (95% confidence interval - 0.57 to 1.03).¹ All sensitivity analysis that were performed pointed to a non-statistically significant effect.

¹ The risk ratios are not symmetrical as intervention is the combination of being randomised to NOST and adhering to it.

Interpretation of effect on primary outcome

The attendees interpreted the findings to be highly uncertain due to the wide 95% CIs, and not convincingly supporting the hypothesis that NOST is an effective intervention for improving compliance with hand hygiene standards, regardless of which group received the intervention. We hypothesise that the staff in the hospital wards that have just started using the tool may be highly motivated, and that this neutralizes any learning effects from having used the tool for a longer period of time. We also observe that compliance was relatively high in both groups (~80%), perhaps prompting a ceiling effect.